

Learning Motivation and Learning Engagements of Grade 2 Pupils: Basis for an Intervention Program

Ailene A. Nuñez

Abstract. This study aimed to develop a targeted intervention program to enhance both learning motivation and engagement of the Grade 2 pupils in Sulop District, Davao Del Sur. The study utilized an explanatory sequential design while incorporating the Input-Process-Output framework. A total of 74 teachers in the Sulop District, Division of Davao del Sur were identified through tabachnick and fidell formula. A researcher-made questionnaire was utilized in the gathering of data. Mean, pearson r, and thematic content analysis used as statistical tools of the study. Results revealed on the levels of learning motivation the grade 2 pupils were extensive which means it was oftentimes evident. On the level of the learning engagement of Grade 2 pupils results revealed was extensive which means that it was also oftentimes evident. Moreover, on the significant relationship between learning motivation and learning engagement, the results appeared a computed p-value which was higher than the .05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted since the value denotes of not having a significant relationship. Lastly, the variables that garnered the lowest mean scores were learning readiness under learning motivation and inquiry skills under learning engagement. The intervention program to enhance the learning engagement and learning motivation of Grade 2 Pupils. three (3) themes were found namely: (1) motivating routines for readiness, (2) curiosity-driven dialogues, and (3) explore and discover stations.

KEY WORDS

1. Learning motivation 2. learning engagement 3. intervention program

Date Received: January 05, 2025 — Date Reviewed: February 15, 2025 — Date Published: April 24, 2025

1. Introduction

Learning engagement is an essential element of successful learning, underpinning cognitive, social, and psychological growth among young learners. Active engagement in the educational process enhances children's academic performance and fosters solid interactions with classmates and teachers. Nevertheless, numerous educational settings persist in facing challenges related to fostering continuous engagement within young pupils. Younger students

encounter difficulties in sustaining high engagement levels, resulting in adverse outcomes such as diminished performance in class and higher rates of dropping out.

Within the Davao del Sur region, research has suggested comparable patterns in student engagement. A study conducted by Quines and Relacion (2022) indicated that numerous Grade 2 students in Davao del Sur encounter difficulties with participation, thus impacting their aca-

demic performance. Their research underscores the essential importance of school atmosphere in promoting student involvement, revealing a substantial correlation among teacher communication habits and engagement among learners. This indicates that strengthening teacher communication might significantly affect the school climate, therefore enhancing levels of engagement within younger students.

A substantial research gap has been identified in recognizing the aspects that impede learning engagement in young children, especially with diverse teaching approaches, classroom settings, and individual variations in emotional and mental growth. Although contemporary research recognizes the significance of motivation in learning, its impact on continuous learner engagement has been barely examined. Furthermore, there is a notable lack of research examining how these elements specifically interact during the unique developmental stage of Grade 2 learners. Consequently, the researcher acknowledges the need for studies that examine the potential relationship between these variables, offering insights to tailor instructional practices and support systems to improve the educational experience for young children.

The study sought to address the following objectives: a.) to determine the level of learning motivation of Grade 2 pupils in terms of curiosity to learn, learning enthusiasm, and learning readiness. b.) to determine the level of learning engagement of Grade 2 pupils in terms of responsiveness of learners, inquiry skills, and

predicting skills. c.) to determine if there a significant relationship between learning motivation and learning engagement of grade 2 pupils, and d.) to develop an intervention program to enhance learning engagement and learning motivation of grade 2 pupils.

At .05 level of significance, the following hypothesis was tested: a.) There is no significant relationship between learning motivation and learning engagement of grade 2 pupils.

The study held significant value for various educational stakeholders by offering insights that improved teaching and learning methodologies. Policymakers gained data supporting early childhood motivation and engagement as key to shaping effective educational policies. Schools were encouraged to enhance instruction and environments to foster academic success and emotional growth. Teachers were guided to adopt diverse, engaging strategies tailored to young learners, while students were inspired to take active roles in their education, understanding how motivation boosts achievement. Lastly, the study laid groundwork for future research into the factors influencing learning motivation and engagement in primary education.

Figure 1 illustrated the advancement of the research. This study utilized the input-process-output paradigm, with the input involving the learning motivation and engagement levels of Grade 2 pupils. The applied process was a survey, with the expected output being an intervention plan aimed at developing learning engagement and motivation among grade 2 pupils.

2. Methodology

The following section outlines the procedures used by the researcher to perform this research study. It includes the population and sampling, instrumentation, data source, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study employed a mixed-method research design using the Explanatory Sequential Approach, which began with the collection and analysis of quan-

titative data, followed by qualitative data to deepen the understanding of results (Creswell Creswell, 2023). Guided by the Input-Process-Output (IPO) Model, the study assessed Grade

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework

2 pupils' learning motivation (curiosity to learn, learning enthusiasm, learning readiness) and engagement (responsiveness of learners, inquiry skills, predicting skills) during the Input Phase. The Process Phase involved statistical analysis to examine the relationship between motivation and engagement, complemented by qualitative interviews for deeper insights. In the Output Phase, findings informed the development of a school-based intervention program aimed at enhancing motivation and engagement, providing a structured, non-experimental exploration of their interplay within the Sulop District, Davao del Sur Division.

2.2. Ethical Considerations—The researcher strictly adhered to ethical standards set by RMC's Research Ethics, covering principles such as social value, informed consent, participant safety, privacy, justice, and transparency. The study aimed to explore the relationship between learning motivation and engagement among Grade 2 pupils in Sulop District, Davao del Sur Division, contributing valuable insights for educational stakeholders, including policymakers, teachers, and parents. Ethical safeguards ensured voluntary participation, informed consent, and confidentiality, especially considering the vulnerability of

teacher-respondents. Risks were addressed through anonymization and secure data handling in compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The researcher, qualified through graduate training and guided by experts, used available resources and maintained neutrality to avoid conflicts of interest. Teachers were treated fairly, briefed transparently, and protected from coercion or professional risk, with their contributions acknowledged through tokens and recognition. The findings were shared in academic and professional settings to promote collaborative efforts and further research in early childhood education.

2.3. Research Respondents—The study involved 74 Grade 2 pupils from public elementary schools in the Sulop District, Davao del Sur Division, selected using Tabachnick and Fidell's (2007) formula for regression analysis and stratified random sampling to ensure proportional representation across schools. To deepen the research, seven pupils were purposively chosen for qualitative interviews, providing valuable insights into developing an intervention program to enhance learning motivation. The study maintained validity by applying strict inclusion criteria, focusing solely on Grade 2 pupils enrolled within the Sulop District, thereby ensuring con-

sistent and targeted data collection.

2.4. Research Instrument—The research utilized structured questionnaires specifically designed for Grade 2 pupils to assess their learning motivation and learning engagement, featuring developmentally appropriate items measured on a 5-point Likert scale. A pilot test with a separate group of learners was conducted to ensure the instrument's clarity and reliability, with Cronbach's alpha values of .924 for moti-

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure—In this study, several key steps were followed to ensure accurate and ethical data collection. First, the researcher obtained official permission from academic authorities, distributed endorsement letters to school heads, and coordinated closely with school staff for efficient survey distribution. Participants were thoroughly briefed on their rights, confidentiality, and the study's purpose. The research instruments underwent rigorous content validation by experts and pilot testing

2.6. Data Analysis—The study utilized several statistical tools to address its research questions. The mean was used to assess Grade 2 pupils' learning motivation as well as their learning engagement. Moreover, Pearson *r* was applied to determine the relationship be-

vation and .838 for engagement, indicating high internal consistency. In the qualitative phase, a researcher-developed interview guide was employed to gather deeper insights into pupils' experiences and challenges related to learning motivation and engagement. Seven pupils were purposively selected for interviews, and the interview guide was validated by a panel of five experts to ensure its relevance and clarity.

to ensure clarity, reliability, and alignment with research goals. Surveys were personally administered to foster trust and allow respondents ample time, while face-to-face interviews were conducted in a supportive environment, with responses recorded for accuracy. After ensuring completeness, questionnaires were securely retrieved and verified. Data were then analyzed using SPSS for quantitative insights and thematic content analysis for qualitative findings, with triangulation enhancing the study's validity and credibility.

tween learning motivation and learning engagement. For the qualitative phase, Thematic Content Analysis (TCA), as described by Anderson (2007), was used to analyze interview and focus group transcripts to identify key themes and provide descriptive insights into the participants' experiences.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter delineated the findings and discussion of the study. The presentation proceeded with a comprehensive discussion of assess the level of learning motivation. Moreover, the next part discussed the level of the learning engagement among Grade 2 pupils. Additionally, it discussed the relationship between these variables. Lastly, based on the findings, the study aims to develop a targeted intervention program to enhance both learning motivation and engagement of the Grade 2 pupils.

3.1. Level of Learning Motivation of Grade 2 Pupils—Table 1 presented a summary

of the level of learning motivation of Grade 2 pupils. These were evaluated in terms of Curios-

ity to Learn, Learning Enthusiasm, and Learning Readiness. The mean scores for each indicator were interpreted as follows: Curiosity to Learn (4.65), marked as Very extensive; Learning Enthusiasm (4.15), marked as extensive; Learning Readiness (3.71), marked as extensive. The findings demonstrated an overall mean rat-

ing of (4.17) marked as extensive. This highlighted that the learning motivation of Grade 2 pupils was oftentimes evident. Of the indicators, Curiosity to Learn received the greatest mean rating of 4.65, categorized as very extensive, whilst Learning Readiness recorded the lowest mean rating of 3.17, categorized as extensive.

Table 1. Level of Learning Motivation of Grade 2 Pupils

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Curiosity to Learn	4.65	Very Extensive
2	Learning Enthusiasm	4.15	Extensive
3	Learning Readiness	3.71	Extensive
Overall		4.17	Extensive

Legend. 1.00–1.79: Not Extensive, 1.80–2.59: Less Extensive, 2.60–3.39: Moderately Extensive, 3.40–4.19: Extensive, 4.20–5.00: Very Extensive

3.2. *Level of Learning Engagement of Grade 2 Pupils*—Table 2 presented a summary of the level of learning engagement of Grade 2 pupils. These were evaluated in terms of Responsiveness of Learners, Inquiry Skills, and Predicting Skills. The mean scores for each indicator were interpreted as follows: Responsiveness of Learners (4.35), marked as Very extensive; Inquiry Skills (3.76), marked as extensive;

Predicting Skills (4.41), marked as Very extensive. The findings demonstrated an overall mean rating of (4.17) marked as extensive. This highlighted that the learning engagement of Grade 2 pupils was oftentimes evident. Of the indicators, Predicting Skills received the greatest mean rating of 4.41, categorized as very extensive, whilst Inquiry Skills recorded the lowest mean rating of 3.76, categorized as extensive.

Table 2. Level of Learning Engagement of Grade 2 Pupils

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Responsiveness of Learners	4.35	Very Extensive
2	Inquiry Skills	3.76	Extensive
3	Predicting Skills	4.41	Very Extensive
Overall		4.17	Extensive

Legend. 1.00–1.79: Not Extensive, 1.80–2.59: Less Extensive, 2.60–3.39: Moderately Extensive, 3.40–4.19: Extensive, 4.20–5.00: Very Extensive

3.3. *Significant Relationship between Learning Motivation and Learning Engagement of Grade 2 Pupils*—Table 3 flaunted the data on the significant relationship between learning motivation and learning engagement of the

grade 2 pupils in Sulop District, Davao del Sur Division. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation (Pearson r) was applied for the two (2) variables on their significant relationship. The results appeared a computed p-value of .085

which was higher than the .05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted since the value denotes of not having a significant relationship.

Furthermore, the computed r-value of 0.20 denotes the correlation between the two variables with which the hypothesis on significant relationship was tested. Clearly, the findings inferred a weak relationship between the learning motivation and learning engagement of the grade 2 pupils in Sulop District, Davao del

Sur Division, suggesting that while there is a slight relationship between the two variables, the strength of the association is minimal. Additionally, the p-value of 0.085 exceeds the standard significance threshold of 0.05, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis (Ho). This means that there is no statistically significant relationship between learning motivation and learning engagement in this specific group of pupils.

Table 3. Significant Relationship between Learning Motivation and Learning Engagement of the Grade 2 Pupils

Variables	r-value	Statistical Description	p-value	Decision
Learning Motivation (x)	0.20	Weak correlation	0.085	Accept Ho
Learning Engagement (y)				

Proposed Intervention Program to Enhance Learning Engagement and Learning Motivation of Grade 2 Pupils

Based on the quantitative results of the study, it was observed that among the indicators of learning motivation and learning engagement, Learning Readiness and Inquiry Skills received the lowest mean scores. This lack of readiness may stem from weak foundational skills, inconsistent study habits, or insufficient internal motivation to initiate learning independently. Similarly, the low mean score in Inquiry Skills, in contrast to the other domains, indicates a need to strengthen students’ abilities to question, explore, and think critically—skills essential for meaningful engagement and deep learning. These findings underscore a crucial insight: while learners possess a strong sense of curiosity and show signs of engagement, their

motivation needs to be strategically supported and translated into actionable learning behaviors. Such a program should include targeted activities that build foundational learning habits, reinforce self-efficacy, and promote active exploration and questioning within the classroom setting.

Figure 2 shows the intervention program to enhance the learning engagement and learning motivation of Grade 2 Pupils. three (3) themes were found namely: (1) Motivating Routines for Readiness, (2) Curiosity-Driven Dialogue, and (3) Explore Discover Stations. The results showed based on the participants’ responses were based on their strategies used to enhance students’ learning readiness, foster curiosity, and develop inquiry skills can inform the design of a program that effectively supports these areas.

Fig. 2. Intervention program can be developed to enhance learning engagement and learning motivation of Grade 2 Pupils

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This study aimed to determine the assess the level of learning motivation in terms of curiosity to learn, learning enthusiasm, and learning readiness. Moreover, to determine the level of the learning engagement among Grade 2 pupils in terms of responsiveness of learners, inquiry skills, and predicting skills. Additionally, it aimed to examine the relationship between these variables. Lastly, based on the findings, the study aims to develop a targeted intervention program to enhance both learning motivation and engagement of the Grade 2 pupils in Sulop District, Davao Del Sur. The following are the significant findings:

4.1. Findings—On the level of the learning motivation of Grade 2 pupils, the findings indicate that the learning motivation of Grade 2 pupils is frequently evident, with an overall extensive rating. Among the indicators, Curiosity to Learn emerged as the strongest, reflecting a very extensive level of interest and eagerness in exploring new knowledge. Learning Enthusiasm was also marked as extensive, demonstrating pupils’ active engagement and positive attitude toward learning. While Learning Readiness received the lowest rating among the three indicators, it was still categorized as extensive, suggesting that pupils generally exhibit preparedness for classroom activities. These results underscore the pupils’ strong intrinsic motivation, with curiosity playing a key role in driving their learning experiences.

On the level of the learning engagement of Grade 2 pupils, the findings indicate that the learning engagement of Grade 2 pupils is frequently evident, with an overall extensive rating. Among the indicators, Predicting Skills emerged as the strongest, reflecting a very extensive level of critical thinking and the ability to anticipate outcomes. Responsiveness of Learners was also marked as very extensive, demonstrating active participation and attentiveness in class. While Inquiry Skills received the lowest rating among the three indicators, it was still categorized as extensive, suggesting that pupils actively engage in questioning and exploration. These results highlight the pupils’ strong engagement in learning, with predicting skills being the most prominent aspect of their cognitive involvement.

On the significant relationship between learning motivation and learning engagement, Clearly, the findings inferred a weak relationship between the learning motivation and learning engagement of the grade 2 pupils in Sulop District, Davao del Sur Division, suggesting that while there is a slight relationship between the two variables, the strength of the association is minimal. Additionally, the p-value exceeds the standard significance threshold, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis (Ho). This means that there is no statistically significant relationship between learning motivation and learning engagement in this specific group of pupils.

4.2. Conclusions—On the intervention program aimed at enhancing Grade 2 pupils' learning motivation and engagement highlights the crucial role of structured routines, curiosity-driven dialogue, and interactive inquiry-based activities. By focusing on motivating students through consistent routines, fostering a sense of curiosity, and providing opportunities for hands-on exploration, the program can significantly boost students' learning readiness and inquiry

skills. These strategies not only create a stable and engaging learning environment but also cultivate the intrinsic motivation needed for sustained academic involvement.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the study's conclusions, several recommendations were proposed: The Department of Education should promote teaching practices that foster curiosity and active learning, while supporting initiatives that enhance learning readiness and participation. School heads are encouraged to implement strategies that boost intrinsic motivation, such as interactive, inquiry-based activities, and provide professional development focused on student engagement. Teachers should design stimulating lessons that build on students' curiosity and enthusiasm, emphasize prediction skills, and support readiness through structured routines. Learners are advised to stay curious, actively participate, and come to class prepared to enhance their engagement. Lastly, future researchers should explore factors influencing the weak relationship between motivation and engagement, including classroom environment, teacher-student dynamics, and peer interactions.

5. References

- Anderson, R. (2007). Thematic content analysis: Descriptive presentation of qualitative data.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2023). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods approaches*. Sage Publications Ltd.
- Quines, L. A., & Relacion, M. C. D. (2022). The mediating effect of school climate on the relationship between teacher communication behavior and student engagement. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 9(11). <https://doi.org/10.46827/ejes.v9i11.4521>
- Republic of the Philippines. (2012). Data privacy act of 2012 (republic act no. 10173).
- Tabachnick, B. G., & Fidell, L. S. (2007). *Using multivariate statistics* (5th). Allyn Bacon/Pearson Education. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2006-03883-000>